

ORGANIZING PROJECT ACTIVITIES BASED ON STEAM TECHNOLOGY IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the significance of the project-based method grounded in STEAM technology for preschool-aged children. It discusses the development of logical thinking skills, design activities, and the advantages of engineering activities in children through STEAM education.*

Keywords: *creativity in children, imagination, emotions, initiative, mobility, adaptability; formation of logical thinking, engineering, design, independence in the educational process, integrated education, STEAM activities and project-based learning, preschool education.*

Technologies Related to Project-based Activities in Preschool Education and Their Impact on Comprehensive Child Development

When discussing technologies associated with project-based activities in preschool education, as well as the technologies used in such activities, their effectiveness in fostering holistic child development becomes evident. The application of STEAM educational technology in the pedagogical process serves as a crucial tool for achieving educational objectives. STEAM activities are inherently practical, with their foundation built upon project design, modeling, and creating. The tasks assigned to children are carried out in stages, progressively building their project planning skills.

The organization of STEAM activities in preschool education incorporates various innovative technologies, including design technology, research technology, learner-centered approaches, game-based technology, and information and communication technology. These technologies encompass the stages of STEAM activities. In a learner-centered approach within STEAM activities, all necessary conditions are created to foster individual creativity.

Project-based activities serve as a didactic tool to enhance children's cognitive and creative development while simultaneously shaping their personal qualities. During the implementation of projects, the knowledge children acquire becomes part of their personal experience. Through experimentation, children seek answers to questions, thereby developing their creative and communication skills.

By employing projects as a form of collaborative developmental activity for children and adults, educators organize educational activities in an engaging, creative, and effective manner. Utilizing projects in preschool education practice has the right to be regarded as a pedagogical innovation since the project method is based on the idea that preschoolers' cognitive activities are directed towards achieving outcomes through collaborative efforts.

Designing Daily Routines in Preschool Education Institutions

The daily routine in a preschool group is determined by the children's age and their life schedule. Each routine activity has a specific duration based on the age capabilities of the children. During the summer period, which extends for 12 hours, the daily routine is slightly adjusted: a single lesson lasting 15 minutes is conducted, and outdoor activities include air and sun exposure

events, followed by water activities after outdoor play. During outdoor time, the educator plans activities such as observing nature and the work of adults, conducting dynamic games at the start, middle, or 30 minutes before the end of the play period.

Children are also assigned simple seasonal tasks, such as collecting leaves in autumn or clearing snow from walkways in winter. Organizing life for young children based on a routine is a challenging task as they lack necessary skills and require the teacher's assistance and attention. The educator engages with each child through a smile, warm words, eye contact, and encouraging questions.

Children in middle groups are more independent. It is important to integrate the external planning of routines with the resolution of educational tasks. The educator also supports children in transitioning between routine activities and ensuring their proper execution. In this process, the educator's ability to correctly plan the day, choose the appropriate activity forms, and implement effective play techniques is crucial.

Children need to sense goodwill and confidence in their abilities from the educator's words. The tone of the educator's voice should never discourage the children or suppress their initiative; instead, it should instill trust and support. Proper organization of a child's life helps cultivate discipline, activity, and independence. Repeating the daily routine builds a sense of stability and promotes skill development, fostering good moods among children.

When planning the pedagogical process, the role of play, practical activities, and their place in the daily routine must be considered, alongside their significance in organizing children's lives and providing comprehensive education. Play is a critical element in forming a cohesive group of children, as it meets their need for activity and communication. Play is regarded as the most important independent activity for preschool-aged children. The content, nature, and organization of games can vary, reflecting their diverse roles in the learning process.

Types and Organization of Games in Preschool Education

Games can be categorized into two types based on their content: **creative games** and **rule-based games**.

Creative Games

Creative games are those invented by the children themselves. These games lack predetermined rules, as children establish their own rules during the gameplay. Creative games are further divided into the following types:

Construction games: Activities involving building or crafting.

Role-playing games: Games where children take on roles and act them out.

Dramatic games: Games that involve staging and performing scenes.

Games with natural materials: Activities utilizing elements like stones, leaves, or sticks.

Rule-Based Games

The content and rules of rule-based games are designed by the educator as part of the planning process. These rules introduce organization and stability into the games, strengthen their structure, and help define subsequent stages, including the complexity of relationships and interactions. Rules also encourage shy or reserved children to participate actively in the games. Rule-based games are further classified into:

Didactic games: Educational tools widely used in preschool education for teaching and upbringing.

Active games: Physical activities that promote movement and coordination.

Musical games: Activities involving music and rhythm.

Didactic games are directly linked to the educational process and act as an auxiliary tool in teaching.

Planning the Educational Process

Planning the educational process is crucial for properly organizing children's lives. Education is a managed process, and its success largely depends on the quality of the didactic design, which is a product of educational technology. Managing learners' cognitive activities based on a didactic plan forms the pedagogical foundation of educational technology.

Just as every process has a beginning and an end, the implementation of a didactic design involves entry and exit points. Between these two points lies a range of methods and tools for achieving educational objectives effectively. Educational technology plays a central role in this process, offering teachers the most effective methods and helping them select the optimal forms of instruction to achieve desired outcomes.

Educational Process Tasks: Preparation and Implementation of an Educational Project

The educational process can be divided into two main stages: preparing an educational project and implementing the project.

1. Preparing an Educational Project

The educational project is the outcome of the teacher's work and contains several general characteristics. At its core lies the collaborative activity that the teacher and learners will undertake in the future. Preparation begins with analyzing the content of the information in accordance with state standard requirements. This analysis focuses on how the elements of content (knowledge, skills, competencies, creative experience, and attitudes) are presented in curricula and instructional materials.

Subsequently, the educational content is examined to define the goals of teaching a particular topic, including the following:

Didactic objectives: Educational and learner-specific goals.

Tools and methods: Tasks, exercises, and control stages tailored to the objectives.

Learning models: Establishing a conceptual framework to integrate all aspects of the educational process.

This phase results in the creation of a comprehensive model for the educational project.

2. Implementing the Educational Project

The implementation phase involves applying the project directly in the educational setting, with emphasis on the following:

Orientation: Introducing learners to the topic's goals and objectives, including tasks, independent assignments, their execution sequence, time allocation, and performance standards. Clear instructions are provided for mastering the material.

Engagement: Stimulating learners' interest in the topic and fostering independent, active engagement. This includes explaining the importance of the topic, encouraging curiosity, and guiding problem-solving efforts. Teachers monitor progress, address challenges, and suggest necessary adjustments.

Processing: Analyzing accumulated knowledge, which involves handling planned and unplanned events, as well as extraordinary or unforeseen situations. Based on the results of ongoing assessments, modifications, additions, or corrections are made to the project.

Evaluation: Drawing conclusions from the gathered knowledge and applying these insights to complex learning situations. This includes analyzing learners' achievements, identifying gaps in knowledge, skills, or creative experience, and providing additional tasks to deepen their understanding of the material.

Through this process, the teacher not only ensures the comprehensive absorption of the educational material but also creates a dynamic learning environment that adapts to the needs and progress of the learners.

3. The Object and Issues of the Design Process

The design process is a crucial aspect of modern pedagogical practice. A well-developed pedagogical technology and other objects ensure that factors harmful to the development of learners as individuals are minimized. Additionally, it creates individual conditions tailored to each learner, as set by the educational system.

The general algorithm of pedagogical design includes the following steps:

Analysis of the design object: Understanding the educational content and its context.

Selection of design forms: Determining the best approaches for delivering the content effectively.

Theoretical support for design: Ensuring the pedagogical foundation is sound and supported by theory.

Methodological support for design: Identifying the strategies, techniques, and approaches that will be used in the teaching process.

Time management: Establishing a timeline to ensure that the material is covered within the designated period.

Material and technical support: Ensuring the availability of necessary resources (tools, materials, equipment) to support the teaching process.

Legal support for design: Ensuring that the pedagogical system and process adhere to legal and ethical standards.

Integration of computers and technology: Leveraging technology to enhance learning experiences and teaching efficiency.

4. Organizing Learners' Educational Activities

In the process of equipping students with knowledge, skills, and competencies, it is essential to assess and monitor their learning progress regularly. Evaluation and motivation are key in determining how effective the teaching methods are and identifying the level of learners' understanding. The effectiveness of the educational system is also influenced by the quality of pedagogical staff training.

A teacher must be able to assess each learner's level of knowledge, choose appropriate learning materials, analyze and synthesize information, and apply the correct educational methods and tools. Teachers should be flexible and adaptable to the needs of their students, making use of suitable techniques based on the pedagogical situation. The ability to analyze their teaching practice and make conclusions is a vital skill for any educator.

The core of the learners' educational activities is the process of knowledge acquisition, which includes the following components:

Receiving educational material: This is the most critical part of the learning process. Properly receiving and understanding the material forms a solid foundation for further learning and academic progress.

Thinking: The learner processes the information, making connections and developing understanding.

Mastery: The learner internalizes the material, moving beyond simple memorization to understanding and application.

Application: The learner applies the acquired knowledge to solve problems and complete tasks, demonstrating their competence.

These components are interrelated and follow each other in sequence, forming the foundation for the entire educational process.

Internal Conditions for Effective Knowledge Acquisition

To achieve effective learning, it is crucial that the learner has an internal need or motivation to engage with the material. Without this internal drive, knowledge may be temporarily retained, such as for exams, but will soon be forgotten once the immediate need (e.g., an exam) is over. The success of learning also depends on the learner's active engagement. If the learner is interested in the material and works diligently, they are more likely to reach the peak of understanding and retention.

Another key internal factor is the learner's ability to understand the material. If the learner does not understand the topic or the provided information, no amount of effort will lead to meaningful learning. The material needs to be connected to previous knowledge for it to be understood and absorbed deeply.

External Factors for Receiving Educational Material

External factors related to receiving educational material are primarily influenced by the content itself. These include the complexity of the material, its use of technical elements, and the degree to which it is practical, abstract, or theoretical. How well these elements are presented can greatly impact the learner's ability to absorb the information.

Memory and Retention

One of the most important components of effective learning is the ability to remember new material and apply it when needed. When learners actively engage with the material, they are better able to retain and use it in practical or theoretical contexts. The effectiveness of memory retention is closely linked to the learner's willpower and personal traits, such as their motivation and discipline.

Skill Development and Application of Knowledge

The ability to apply knowledge in practical situations demonstrates the level of mastery the learner has achieved. When learners are able to use their theoretical knowledge in practical settings—such as completing laboratory work or solving real-world problems—they show a deeper understanding of the material. The process of applying knowledge helps to reinforce and expand it, turning surface-level understanding into more comprehensive and solidified knowledge.

Independent work is also critical in organizing and reinforcing the learner's cognitive activities. Self-directed learning, or self-development, plays a significant role in expanding personal knowledge and skills. In many cases, this process is largely the responsibility of the learner, as they take initiative to improve and grow in their educational journey.

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